

PHYSICAL SCIENCES

SUPERCONDUCTIVITY

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Abstract

Since the publication of this work, it has become a canonical work on the theory of high-temperature superconductivity (HTSC), based on the proposed and developed theory of quantum exchange forces in condensed media, which made it possible to elucidate the mechanism for the formation of Cooper complexes, which provides a consistent account of long-range exchange forces and makes it possible to spontaneously explain the pairing of electrons that occurs both at large and relatively small distances. In this case, the manifestation of spin correlations in superconductors and the phase transformations arising in them are observed. The effect of exchange overlap during fluctuations creates attractive forces that have a long-range order and act on electrons. The main way to increase the limit of the superconducting transition temperature in ceramics is to use materials with the lowest possible molecular weight. The fluctuation hypothesis of the superconducting state explains the necessity of using metal alloys highly enriched with oxygen.

The discovery of high-temperature superconductivity (HTSC) encourages us to reconsider the previously accepted concepts of Cooper pairing of electrons and to reveal a pairing mechanism that is effective for both pure metals and ceramic compounds. It was found that internodal overlaps of wave packets can lead to the formation of an energy gap. In this case, the greater the electrical conductivity of the material in the normal state, the lower the critical transition temperature. Therefore, in pure metals, it is minimal. A certain level of amorphism stimulates superconductivity and creates an HTSC situation.

Keywords: quantum mechanics, quantum calculations, long-range effect, superconductivity effect, electron-photon interaction, unified quantum concept of forces determining long-range order in condensed media, theory of exchange forces, Bloch function, intercenter electron exchange, overlap of electron shells, overlap integrals, Cooper couples back.

The property of superconductivity means the complete absence of resistance to electric current. The substance passes into the superconducting state when the temperature is lowered abruptly, the corresponding temperature is called the superconducting transition temperature. The phenomenon of superconductivity was discovered in 1911 by the Dutch scientist Kamerling-Onnes while studying the dependence of the electrical resistance of mercury on temperature. It turned out that at a temperature (in absolute scale) $T_c = 4.2^\circ \text{K}$ the resistance of the mercury sample suddenly disappeared and was not found at all temperatures below this.

For various substances that are in a crystalline state, the temperature T_c varies within a fairly wide range: from supercold temperatures - fractions of a degree Kelvin - to relatively moderate temperatures - one hundred (and slightly higher) degrees in the same Kelvin scale. Until recently, most of the theoretical and experimental research was devoted to the study of superconductivity in pure metals and their alloys. Their goal was not only to elucidate the physical mechanism of superconductivity, but also to obtain materials with the highest superconducting transition temperature. Movement in this direction was very slow. Over many decades of persistent experimentation, the temperature has been raised from a few degrees to a value only slightly higher than twenty degrees Kelvin (in alloys of niobium and germanium). Only in 1985, i.e. almost three quarters of a century after the discovery of Kamerling-Onnes,

a radical breakthrough was made - the phenomenon of high-temperature superconductivity (HTSC) was discovered. This discovery was made in 1986 by Swiss scientists T. Bednorz and Müller, working in Zurich in the research laboratory of UBM (USA). They discovered HTSC not in metals or their alloys (it was in these good conductors that they tried with fanatical persistence to increase the temperature of the superconducting transition), but in Ba - La - Cu - O systems,

which are ceramic compounds. Under normal conditions, these connections are insulators rather than conductors. But it is in them that a superconducting transition occurs, and at higher temperatures than in the "best" metal connections. Already in the first experiments with ceramics, the transition temperature exceeded 30°K .

The announcement of the discovery of HTSC served as a starting signal in a powerful competitive assault. All leading laboratories of the world immediately joined the search for ceramics based on metal oxide compounds, which include elements of group II of the periodic table of D. I. Mendeleev and rare earth elements. First, strontium was added in a certain proportion. The temperature in the LaBaSrCuO compound increased to 40°K .

Then they began to "shuffle" the rare earth elements that are part of the ceramics. Ceramic based Y - Ba - Cu - O was

a record temperature was reached $T_c = 92^\circ \text{K}$ - a record for 1987. Then, as in sports, each subsequent

year led to the overthrow of the records of the previous year. In 1990, the value $T_c = 120^\circ\text{K}$, obtained by Japanese researchers in ceramics with a "lightweight" composition, was recorded as a record: titanium, vanadium were used instead of the heavy elements lanthanum, yttrium, and copper turned out to be superfluous - it turned out to be important to saturate the compound with oxygen.

The discovery of HTSC means a true revolution in technology. The use of electronic instruments and devices, electrical machines and transmission lines, powerful magnetic systems that operate at not too low temperatures and do not lose energy for ohmic heating, leads to a significant increase in their efficiency and, consequently, to a huge economic effect.

The first microscopic theory of superconductivity was constructed in 1957 by J. Bardin, L. Cooper and J. Schrieffer (BCS theory). A great contribution to the development of the theory was made by N.N. Bogolyubov. In this theory, it is assumed that the superconducting current in a crystal is carried not by conduction electrons isolated from each other, but by their pairwise groups - the so-called Cooper pairs [2]. The electrons included in each of these pairs are linked to each other by some effective attractive forces. Effective because if we ignore the influence of the crystal lattice, then the electrons only repel each other through the Coulomb forces. Only deformations or oscillatory motions of ions in the lattice sites can, as it were, extinguish these repulsive forces and, moreover, lead to the resulting attraction between electrons. This is similar to how two objects lying on a surface with a depression or notch begin to approach each other, as if experiencing mutual attraction.

In a crystal, such deformations are, as a rule, positively charged and play the role of such depressions for electrons. The interaction of the latter with lattice vibrations, whose carriers from the point of view of quantum mechanics are quasi-particles-photons (sound quanta), is called electron-photon [3,4]. It leads, according to the BCS theory, to the formation of Cooper pairs. The electrons in each pair have oppositely directed momentum vectors and spin moments, and the distance between them can be relatively very significant - about $b = 10^{-4}\text{cm}$, so that the electrons included in this pair can be separated by a significant number of particles that are not related to this pair. This is the effect of long-range interaction or the influence of long-range order forces in a crystal. The binding energy in each pair is estimated to be $\Delta \sim 10^{-4} \div 10^{-5}\text{eV}$, so that the pairs are rather weakly related to each other. However, such a relation is sufficient to explain the effect of superconductivity.

In addition to the binding energy, Δ electrons also have a kinetic energy, which on average is much higher Δ (by four orders of magnitude). The energy levels even before electron pairing, i.e. in the normal state of the crystal, are filled with particles sequentially - from the lowest to the Fermi level E_f . Pairing only adds a small negative energy ($-\nabla$) to each pair. A conglomerate of electrons is formed, called a condensate. In the superconducting state, all condensate moves with a common velocity V , creating an electric current. If deceleration

were in effect, then the energy of the electron that had the maximum speed $\vartheta_f + V$, Where $\vartheta_f = \sqrt{2E_f/m}$, m is the electron mass, would change, for example, by the value

$$m(\vartheta_f + V)^2/2 - m(\vartheta_f - V)^2/2 = 2m\vartheta_f V$$

But then the pair would be destroyed, for this it is required to expend energy Δ . Therefore, the inequality must be satisfied

$$V > \frac{\Delta}{2m\vartheta_f} = V_c \quad (1)$$

here V_c is the critical current velocity, above which the state of superconductivity is destroyed. The corresponding electric current density $I_c = enV_c$, where $e = -1.6 \cdot 10^{-19}\text{C}$ is the charge

electron, $n = 10^{28}\text{m}^{-3}$ - the concentration of electrons in the metal. According to Maxwell's equation, the induction created by this current is:

$$B_c = \mu_0 j_c b = \frac{\mu_0 \Delta b n}{2m\vartheta_f} \quad (2)$$

$\mu_0 = 4\pi \cdot 10^{-7} \frac{\text{H}}{\text{m}}$ vacuum magnetic permeability. With typical values of the following parameters included in the last formula: $\Delta = 10^{-4}\text{eV} = 1.6 \cdot 10^{-23}\text{J}$; $n = 10^{28}\text{m}^{-3}$; $m = 0.91 \cdot 10^{-30}$

kg ; $b = 10^{-6}\text{m}$; $= 10^6\text{m/s}$ we obtain an estimate of $B_c \approx 0.05\text{ Tesla}$. At such fields and their high values, the superconductor passes into the normal state: a strong magnetic field and the superconducting state turn out to be incompatible with each other. This is the well-known Meissner-Ochsenfeld effect, discovered back in 1933.

The discovery of HTSC caused some confusion in the scientific world. The fact is that the electron-photon interaction limits the transition temperature from above T_c . The theory predicts a maximum of the latter at about 40°K . In reality, however, in ceramics it turns out to be much higher, and this means that the already familiar theoretical concept must be revised. In addition, the fact that HTSC is observed in compounds that are less perfect in their structure than, it would seem, ideal photon carriers - metallic compounds. In theoretical terms, all the advantages in terms of the intensity of the electron-photon interaction are on the side of metals, but in reality the situation is just the opposite. Obviously, this requires a change, perhaps a radical one, and an interpretation of the entire complex of phenomena associated with superconductivity.

In [3], the physical concept of HTSC based on consistent application of the theory of exchange forces in quantum mechanics. It turns out that such a concept is capable of explaining the HTSC phenomenon both qualitatively and quantitatively, in accordance with the available experimental data. The theory of exchange forces, as is well known, is the basis of the theory of ferromagnetism and antiferromagnetism. It is probably no coincidence that the observed manifestations of correlations of the spin moments of electrons in superconductors and the phenomenon of superconductivity are realized together and are closely related to each other: this is a consequence of the universality of the unity of the quantum exchange forces acting in this case.

The Bloch function describing the state of the conduction electron is equal to the product of the amplitude function and the exponential factor associated with translation. The amplitude part is determined in a particular model mainly based on the application of a variational procedure. As soon as this function is known, the square of its modulus determines the rate of decrease in the electron density near one or another center - an ionic or atomic lattice site. The Bloch functions themselves are functions of the one-electron approximation. It is natural to raise the question of the symmetrization of the system of electronic states. The symmetrization procedure, which follows from the indistinguishability principle, is fairly familiar in molecular orbital theory. As for the Bloch states, such a procedure is not carried out for some reason. But without carrying out such a procedure in an explicit form, it is apparently impossible to consistently take into account the effects associated with intercenter electron exchange. True, certain energy contributions due to the exchange are taken into account when writing model Hamiltonians of the Hubbard Hamiltonian type. However, the essential parameters included in these Hamiltonians are phenomenological. It seems to us that such parameters can be calculated directly using the explicit symmetrization procedure.

When calculating the overlaps of electron shells and the resulting energy contributions, it is necessary to number the electrons, "tying" them to certain nodal centers as centers of attraction. The property of the spatial periodicity of the amplitude factors of the Bloch functions is retained, but the reading of the radius-vectors of the numbered electrons changes in accordance with the specified "binding".

At the first stage of the implementation of such a calculation procedure, only successive pairwise overlaps of electrons, which can be separated by several or several tens of atoms, are initially taken into account. It is clear that the energy effect of exchange is completely equivalent to the effect of interatomic exchange in molecular compounds. It suffices to point to the Heitler - London method for calculating the energy terms of diatomic molecules. As in molecular compounds, the binding interelectronic forces acting in a crystalline solid are attractive forces and are due to the exchange overlapping of electron shells. The only difference here is that, due to a weaker decrease in the electron densities corresponding to the conduction bands in crystals, the interelectronic exchange in subsequent crystals has a significantly long-range character, while in the case of

molecules, the exchange forces are short-range. Therefore, in relation to the action of the exchange, solid-state bonds determine the forces of long-range order, and the formations caused by them, for example, Cooper pairs, turn out to be analogous to compounds of the molecular type. The emerging currents are also molecular currents - these currents are not accompanied by dissipative losses, i.e. do not experience ohmic resistance, just as do not experience its electron currents in the NO molecule, the main term of which is the term 2Π .

The degree of overlap of localized electron wave

functions depends on the rate of decrease of Bloch amplitudes with distance from the center of localization. In the model of successively located potential wells, the attenuation coefficient is approximately $0.7 (mV_0)^{1/2}$, where V_0 is the depth of the potential

wells, m is the effective mass of carriers. For good conductors, the energy $V_0 \approx 10\text{eV}$, and damping occurs at a distance of the order of two or three Bohr radii, if the effective mass is close to the mass of the electron. The distance at which the exchange forces can still act is comparable to the distance between lattice nodes. In cermets, the binding energy of carriers is tens of times less, so that electrons sufficiently distant from each other are involved in the exchange bond, namely, at distances of the order of 10^{-7}cm or more.

of the Cooper pair in the exponent. This difference is almost always less 10^{-6}cm^{-1} , so that interference cannot "extinguish" the exchange overlap at distances, $\geq 10^{-6}$ see Fig.

The model of the exchange interaction of superconducting electrons considered in this work is capable of overcoming the difficulties of theoretically describing superconducting metal oxide compounds that simultaneously exhibit antiferromagnetic properties.

The antiparallel orientation of spins in itself in each pair of electrons interacting through exchange forces is quite understandable: the coordinate part with a certain type of permutation symmetry corresponds to the minimum energy of the pair. However, for example, in a flat triangular lattice, if we consider pairwise overlaps of electron shells belonging to the vertices of triangles as centers of attraction, pairwise antiferromagnetic ordering of electron spin moments is obviously impossible. There is a kind of frustration - a set of conflicting requirements due to the equality of several possible solutions. To overcome the contradictions, F. Anderson proposed a model of "resonant valence bond", which assumes that the spin of an electron located at one of the vertices changes direction all the time. However, frustration is not eliminated in such a model, but, on the contrary, it manifests itself especially clearly if we turn to square lattices, or if we take into account the interaction with the nearest vertices adjacent to the square under consideration.

When using the model of exchange interactions, frustration is eliminated in any case if simple physical factors are taken into account. Indeed, as noted above, the overlap integrals of the Bloch functions vanish due to the interference effect if the momenta of the interacting particles are not close in magnitude (and direction). This means that the electrons in Cooper pairs have close momenta, otherwise the bond between the electrons of the selected pair is lost. The probability that the third electron closest to the pair under consideration has exactly the same value of momentum as that of the electrons of the pair is obviously negligible. The third electron turns out to be superfluous in relation to this pair! Its spin has an arbitrary direction, and one can speak of "resonance" in this sense. However, it is better to state that the spin state of neighboring electrons is indifferent with respect to the selected pair.

From what has been said above, it follows that the ordering of the arrangement of ionic centers in a crystal

is very important, since it is precisely this order that determines the pattern of interference overlap of electron shells. It is also clear that the mismatch in magnitude of the wave vectors that determine the Bloch functions can lead to a shift in the overlap regions, such that the interference pattern is violated and, as a result, the exchange integrals, on which the electron binding energy depends, vanishes. As simple numerical estimates show, this happens if the relative change in the distances between the atomic or ion "binding" centers changes by a value comparable to the relative detuning of the electron wave vectors.

Relative and Statistically Averaged Displacement of Neighboring Ionic Centers in Metal Oxides at Temperatures

$T \sim 100K$ is on the order of $10^{-4}cm$. The corresponding relative change in the distances between the "binding" centers for Cooper pairs removed by 10-100 atomic length constants, taking into account the wandering law (i.e., taking into account the factor $\sqrt{N}$, where N is the number of ions in the segment of the chain separating these centers) will also be a value of the order of several percent, i.e. just on the order of the ratio of the energy gap of the superconductor to the Fermi energy.

So, we have a self-consistent qualitative picture that describes the physical state of the electrons that create the HTSC effect. Let's move on to a quantitative analysis of the situation [3].

The effectiveness of exchange effects in high-temperature superconductors is revealed purely experimentally. For example, diffraction peaks were studied during X-ray scattering in materials such as bismuth ceramics before and after the stage of their transition to the superconducting state. It was found that copper oxide interlayers by themselves do not yet guarantee the occurrence of the HTSC phenomenon. However, this phenomenon can be explained if we assume that the electrons in a given layer of copper oxide are coupled by exchange forces with the electrons of neighboring layers of copper oxide. In this case, the role of the "organizer" of the Bloch electronic states is attributed to the metallized interlayer separating these ions. As if unusual quasi-molecules are formed, the core of which is a two-dimensional metal layer, and the bond in the quasi-molecule is ultimately due to the action of Coulomb forces.

In [1, 4],

experimental consequences of annealing on the structure of bismuth-strontium ceramics and the effect of annealing on the state of HTSC.

It was found that annealing practically does not change the type of crystal symmetry in these materials. However, it affects in two respects: it leads to compression of the unit cell of the crystal in the direction of its main axis and at the same time increases the amount of oxygen and electrons associated with it. In addition, annealing leads to some ordering of intrinsic defects of the crystal lattice, such as oxygen vacancies. From the standpoint of the HTSC theory presented here, a decrease in the distance between centers and an increase in ordering leads to an increase in the exchange forces.

Consider the interaction of electrons and singly

charged ions A, B , to which the electrons "belong", and R_0 - the distance between the ions, and the entire system of charges is enclosed inside a sphere of radius R

, which will be defined below. The term "belongs" in accordance with the analysis carried out in the previous paragraph, that for each of the electrons, the center of reference of the radius vector of the particle is determined, and in the approximation, for example, of strong coupling, the wave function of the electron decreases with distance from the corresponding center. In this case, the Bloch function of the first of the electrons is equal to $\psi_{k_1}(r_1) = u_{k_1}(r_1) \exp(i\vec{k}_1 \vec{r}_1)$

and the radius vector r_1 is measured from the nucleus A , while the analogous function for the second electron

$$\psi_{k_2}(r_2) = u_{k_2}(r_2) \exp(i\vec{k}_2 \vec{r}_2)$$

and the vector r_2 is counted from the nucleus B , here $k_{1,2}$ are the wave vectors of the electrons.

Generally speaking, the amplitude functions $u(r)$ decrease with

distance from the centers, so that the effective radii of the electron clouds are $\frac{1}{2}(R_0 + a) > \frac{1}{2}R$, and these clouds form some kind of overlap of the view of the thickness segment a .

Taking into account the principle of indistinguishability, the state of electrons in the sphere under consideration is described by a function symmetrized with respect to permutations of electrons. Using this function to describe the interaction of electron-ion complexes in a crystal, this equation has the form:

$$T_c^\circ = \hbar \frac{\omega_i}{4k_B \Delta(T_c^\circ)}, \Delta(T_c^\circ) = \left(\frac{m E_F^2}{k_B T_c^\circ \hbar w_i M} \right) \quad (3)$$

For a type I superconductor such as tin, assuming $M = 10^{-22}g$; $E_F = 10^{11} \text{ erg}$; $w_i = 3 \cdot 10^{13} \text{ 1/s}$; $T_c^\circ \leq 10^\circ$

In the case of high-temperature superconductivity observed in ceramics, the Fermi energy decreases with respect to normal materials by about an order of magnitude. At the same time, the molecular weight decreases in the same ratio, since there is a lot of oxygen in the composition of ceramics. As a result, the logarithmic factor $\Delta \leq 1$ and the transition temperature $T_c^\circ = \hbar w_i / 4k_B \cong 100^\circ K$, which is observed in experience.

Hence it follows that there is an upper limit of the superconducting transition temperature, which is determined by the energy of the ionic Langmuir quantum. The main way to increase the limit is to use materials with the lowest possible molecular weight. This is exactly what happens in HTSC practice: there is a tendency to use alloys in which titanium or vanadium is used instead of lanthanum, and the compounds are highly enriched in oxygen.

The considered mechanism creates pairing of particles on $R = \frac{2\pi}{k_F} \sqrt{(E_F/k_F T_c^\circ)} \sim 10^{-5} \text{ see}$ For ceramic materials, the ratio of the energy gap and the transition temperature, expressed in energy units, is of the order of

$$e^2 k_F / 4 E_F \sim 1.$$

. It is this kind of relation F or proportionality that

is observed in the experiment. Thus, the fluctuation hypothesis of the superconducting state explains, and relatively freely, the characteristic features of the observed phenomena, i.e. contains the principle of their explanation.

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